

	Values of Requirement RVnc ↓ for Procedures (n)*																	Values of Competence Cnc ↓ Procedures (n)																		
	Heuristic			Meta-Heuristic			Deterministic-exact			Stochastic / Dynamic Approaches			AI-based			Heuristic			Meta-Heuristic			Deterministic-exact			Stochastic / Dynamic Approaches			AI-based								
Field of Competence (c)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	Company-specific Competence Value (CVc) ↓	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	
Skill Level of Employees	1	1	1	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	3	4	4	4	5	4	5	2	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-2	-2	-2	-3	-2	-3	
Technical Infrastructure	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	5	4	5	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-2	-1	-2
*Values are based on a literature evaluation (cf. General Evaluation of Competence for Procedure)																			0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-2	-2	-2	-5	-3	-5	← Competence bar